

Development of an analysis strategy for integrated network analysis of multi- omics data

Pradeep ERANTI

Advisors: Florence DEMENAIIS and Emmanuelle BOUZIGON

Group of Genomic Epidemiology of Multifactorial Diseases
UMRS-1124, Université de Paris, Inserm

1 Introduction

Multifactorial diseases, such as cancers, cardiovascular diseases, neuro-psychiatric diseases, asthma and allergic diseases stem from the complex interplay of multiple genetic and environmental factors. The effect sizes attributable to individual factors, especially genetic factors, are likely to be small in most of the cases. Recent advances in high-throughput -omics technologies have greatly increased our ability to measure thousands of molecular variations at genome-wide scale. Naturally, by taking advantage of the technological advancements, genome-wide associations studies (GWASs) have become common practice in search of genetic factors underlying multifactorial diseases. Though GWAS based on huge sample sizes have been able to pinpoint a number of novel loci underlying the disease, they are able to explain only part of the heritable component of disease. GWAS focuses on testing the association of disease with individual SNPs present across the whole genome and only SNPs passing the multiple-testing corrected genome-wide significant level ($P = 5 \times 10^{-8}$) are reported, leaving many SNPs being missed out in the downstream analysis. Indeed, these association analyses hamper the detection of genetic variants with small marginal effects, such as those interacting with other genetic variants or with environmental factors. Similar observations can be made with other omics studies, such as epigenome-wide association studies (EWAS) or transcriptome-wide association studies (TWAS). All of this fosters the development of alternative strategies for identifying genetic factors associated with disease. In addition, the idea of integrating multiple omics datasets is appealing because a single omics dataset is unlikely to provide a comprehensive insight into the complex disease process and such integrated analysis has been proven successful (Ma *et al.*, 2020; Eddy *et al.*, 2020; Karczewski and Snyder, 2018).

To appreciate the success of genome-wide approaches and also to include the factors with small marginal effect into the downstream analysis, methods integrating the biological knowledge together with genome-wide study findings have been proposed. Among these methods, network analysis that integrates the genome-wide results with a biological network to identify sub-networks enriched in disease association signals has become more broadly used (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Liu *et al.*, 2017a; Y. Liu *et al.*, 2017b; Azencott *et al.*, 2013; Jia *et al.*, 2011). The driving force behind this approach is the “guilt-by-association” principle, which states that connected genes or gene products usually participates in either same or related cellular functions (Oliver, 2000; Wolfe *et al.*, 2005). It can be argued that network analysis provides a promising approach to discover functionally related genes acting jointly with small marginal effects.

Asthma is a multifactorial disease resulting from the effects and interactions of multiple genetic and environmental factors and is characterized by varying age at onset and clinical manifestations. It is known that some genetic factors associated with childhood-onset asthma differ from those associated with adult-onset asthma; and allergy is more prevalent

in childhood-onset asthma than in adult-onset asthma. Allergy is characterized by increased levels of total and specific Immunoglobulin E (IgE) levels and positive responses to skin prick tests to allergens. Total serum IgE is a central mediator of allergic inflammation, as encountered in childhood-onset asthma (Burrows *et al.*, 1989; Andiappan *et al.*, 2016). It is likely that shared biological mechanisms are underlying IgE production and risk of childhood-onset asthma. While the number of genetic variants associated with asthma risk has been increasing in recent studies (Ferreira *et al.*, 2019; Demenais *et al.*, 2018), GWAS of IgE levels have identified a small number of genetic variants which account for only 1-2% of the variation in serum IgE. Epigenetic mechanisms, such as CpG methylation, regulate the expression of genes that may play a role in IgE production. Recent epigenome-wide association studies of total IgE have revealed CpG sites in promoter regions of genes accounting for a variation in the total serum IgE that is tenfold higher than that derived from large SNP genome-wide association studies (Liang *et al.*, 2015). Thus, it can be hypothesized that the integration of results (summary statistics) from GWAS for childhood-onset asthma (CoA) and EWAS for IgE levels can provide insight in shared biological pathways underlying IgE regulation and risk of allergic asthma occurring in childhood.

The goal of the current study was to develop an analysis strategy to integrate the results of CoA GWAS and IgE EWAS with a publicly available biological interaction network to identify two gene modules enriched with association signals towards the respective phenotype of interest (Childhood-onset Asthma or IgE levels) and to characterize the genes and pathways shared by these two modules. Usually biological interaction networks present the relationship between genes in various forms, such as, relation between gene products (proteins), gene co-expression. So, as a first step, the P-values from the genome-wide association results must be converted into gene-level P-values, followed by imposing them onto the network to construct a scored biological network. Then, the SigMod method (Liu *et al.*, 2017b) can be used to identify a strongly interconnected module enriched in association signals. Inspection of the two modules identified from the CoA-GWAS and IgE-EWAS data and functional enrichment analysis can reveal biologically meaningful processes shared by CoA and IgE and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the molecular mechanisms involved in allergic asthma. The results presented in this report validate the proposed analysis strategy which can be further extended to large datasets which have been recently generated and other types of omics data.

2 Materials

2.1 Childhood-onset Asthma (CoA) GWAS datasets

To identify a gene module associated with Childhood-Onset Asthma (CoA), we utilized the GWAS datasets generated by the European GABRIEL consortium, which aimed at identifying the key genetic factors associated with the occurrence of asthma from 23 studies consisting of genome-wide data for 10,365 cases and 16,110 controls (Moffatt *et al.*, 2010);

see the original publication for more details about data collection. In our current study, we focused on nine childhood-onset GWASs (ALSPAC, BAMSE, CAPPs, ECRHS, MAGICs, MAS, SLSJ, TOMSK, UFA) with cumulative sample size of 3,031 cases and 2,893 controls. Genotyping for all the samples have been performed using the the Illumina Human610-Quad Beadchip. During the quality control (QC) process of 582,892 SNPs, SNPs with call rate lower than 95% or minor allele frequency (MAF) lower than 0.01, or with Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium p -value $< 10^{-4}$ were removed. In each GWAS dataset, imputations at genome-level were performed using MACH 1.0 software and Hapmap2 reference panel (release 21). The QC filtering included removal of SNPs with imputation quality score of less than 0.5 and MAF less than 0.01, which resulted in a total 2,370,689 SNPs. In each of these studies, association between asthma and individual SNPs was performed using a logistic regression model which includes allele dosage for each SNP and principal components to account for the population structure. A meta-analysis of the nine GWAS was performed using a random-effects model implemented in STATA V12 (distributed by Stata Corporation, College Station, Texas, USA).

The outcome of the meta-analysis (2.3 million SNP P-values) was used as input to the network analysis.

2.2 IgE EWAS datasets

In order to identify the gene module associated with IgE levels, we used the EWAS datasets generated in two study populations: Epidemiological study on the Genetics and Environment of Asthma (EGEA with follow-up over 3 time periods) and Medical Research Council for Eczema (MRCE). DNA Methylation profiling was performed using MethylC-Capture Sequencing for blood samples from 599 asthmatics of the EGEA cohort and from 192 children (80 asthmatics, 112 non-asthmatics) of the MRCE cohort. This approach based on bisulfite sequencing allows targeting about ~5M CpGs near regulatory elements of immune cell such as enhancers and promoters which are not all covered with existing Illumina arrays. After applying a number of quality control procedure and filtering steps (Allum *et al.*, 2019) 2.8M CpGs were available for analysis. Epigenome-wide association study (EWAS) between methylation profiles (distribution of number of methylated reads among total number of reads for each subject) and IgE levels was conducted using a Binomial Mixed Model while adjusting for age, sex, smoking status and measured blood cell proportions (monocytes, lymphocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils and basophils). Analyses were performed in EGEA and MRCE datasets separately. The results from these two EWAS were meta-analyzed using a fixed-effects model (Beaumier *et al.*, 2019)

In total, there were 2,812,044 CpGs with meta-analysis results (P-values of association with IgE) that were used as input for the network analysis.

3 Methods

3.1 Computing gene-level statistic from SNP-level or CpG-level statistics

A GWAS/EWAS is performed at SNP-level or CpG-level, whereas the biological network knowledge is generally given at gene/protein-level. To bridge this gap, SNPs or CpGs need to be first mapped to genes, followed by, calculating gene-level P-values from SNP-level or CpG-level P-values, here the P-values resulting from the meta-analyses.

In case of SNP to gene assignment, SNPs were assigned to genes using the information from Genome Reference Consortium Human Build 37 (GRCh37/hg19) and NCBI dbSNP database. Once the SNPs were assigned to genes, the gene-level P-values were calculated using fastCGP (Liu *et al.*, 2017a), an efficient and exact method, which is implemented by taking advantage of the Circular Genomic Permutation (CGP) strategy proposed earlier (Cabrera *et al.*, 2012). The permutation-based approach, CGP, considers the full genome as a circle starting from Chromosome 1 to Chromosome 22, followed by arranging the SNP-level P-values on the circle according to the SNP positions. A CGP sample is generated by rotating the circle from a randomly chosen position and reassigning the P-values to the SNP at new position. The gene P-value, P_g , is calculated by assigning the lowest P-values among all the P-values of the SNPs mapping to that gene. Thus, calculated gene P-values might be biased by the gene length, as it is well known that the longer genes tend to have increased number of SNPs mapped to it and thereby higher chances of having a lower best SNP P-value by chance. This method calculates the corrected P_g as $P_{corrected} = 1 - l/(L + 1)$, where L denotes the number of CGP permutations, l as the number of permuted samples with $P_{\pi,g} > P_g$; $P_{\pi,g}$ denotes the best SNP P-value of gene g on a permutation sample. fastCGP considers all unique CGP samples to calculate the best P-value based on the permutation strategy. In such setting, the total number of CGP samples (L) equals to the number of SNPs overlaid on to the circle and L is calculated without generating any CGP sample. The implementation of the method fastCGP is available at: <https://github.com/YuanlongLiu/fastCGP>.

The GREAT annotation tool (McLean *et al.*, 2010) was used for CpG-gene assignment based on hg19 human genome assembly. CpGs were assigned to gene(s) when CpGs were located within 5Kb on either side of a gene's transcription start site. GREAT tool was accessed using the Bioconductor package rGREAT (Gu, 2020). Once the CpGs were mapped to gene(s), gene-level P-values were calculated using fastCGP approach as describer earlier.

3.2 Construction of a scored Protein-Protein Interaction Network

To construct a scored network, two types of input data are required: list of gene-level statistics and a network representing biological knowledge through gene-gene relationships. Among many types of biological networks, protein-protein interaction (PPI) network constitutes a major share which describes various types of relationships among genes and

their gene products, including physical interaction, gene co-expression, and their co-occurrence in the literature. Hence, it is treated as important resource in performing integrative network analysis of genome-wide data. The Search Tool for the Retrieval of INteracting Genes/proteins (STRING) is currently the largest PPI database covering 24,584,628 proteins from 5,090 organisms, out of which 19,257 belongs to Homo Sapiens (Szklarczyk *et al.*, 2019). The connections among these proteins carry a score which denotes the approximate confidence, on a scale of zero to one, of the functional association between the linking proteins being true and is derived from multiple sources of evidence, such as, co-expression, text-mining, biochemical/genetic data (experiments), previously curated pathway and protein-complex knowledge (databases), and through genomic prediction (neighborhood, fusion, gene co-occurrence). The human PPI network (GeneNet) from the STRING database was downloaded (<https://string-db.org/>) and the gene P-values, calculated above, were converted into gene scores using the inverse normal distribution ($z = \phi^{-1}(1 - P)$). Then, the calculated gene scores were overlaid on to the GeneNet to construct a scored network.

3.3 Identification of a gene module enriched with disease/trait association signals

The SigMod method was used to identify a **Strongly Interconnected Gene MODule** maximally associated with the disease from the input scored GeneNet. Let us assume the scored GeneNet as G , then $G = (V, A)$; where V represents the genes as nodes and A represents the adjacency matrix consisting of the connections among the genes (V). SigMod treats the task to identify the list of genes present in the interconnected module as a selection problem: assume u as a vector of binary variable which denotes whether a gene V_p is selected ($u_p = 1$) or not ($u_p = 0$). SigMod identifies a module that is enriched in high score genes and tend to be strongly interconnected from a node-scored network by solving a maximization problem:

$$\arg \max_{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n} f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, \lambda, \eta), \quad (1)$$

where the objective function f is defined as

$$f(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, \lambda, \eta) = \underbrace{\sum_i z_i u_i}_{\text{Association}} + \lambda \underbrace{\sum_{i \neq j} A_{ij} u_i u_j}_{\text{Interconnectivity}} - \eta \underbrace{\sum_i I(u_i = 1)}_{\text{Sparsity}}. \quad (2)$$

In the objective function f , z_i is the score of the i^{th} gene, A_{ij} is the interaction weight between i^{th} and j^{th} gene ($A_{ij} = 0$ if there is no interaction), u_i is an indicator variable indicating whether a gene is selected ($u_i = 1$) or not ($u_i = 0$). λ is the interconnection tuning parameter and a big λ value will lead to select a strongly interconnected module. η is the sparsity tuning parameter and a big η value will lead to select less genes.

For fixed values of λ and η , solving the optimization problem defined by Equation (1) will determine whether a gene is selected or not i.e. the value of each u_i . This maximization problem can be solved exactly using a graph-cut algorithm (Azencott *et al.*, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2017b).

To determine the values of tuning parameters, λ and η (in Eq. 2), which leads to the selection of an optimal gene module, the authors (Liu *et al.*, 2017b) proposed a hierarchical procedure that includes three steps: (1) do an exhaustive search for k equally spaced λ values in $[\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}]$ and compute for each λ the gene selection path $P(\lambda)$ over a range of η values to collect all modules with module size less than n_{max} (maximum number of genes to be selected); (2) compute the size difference between consecutive modules (named size jump) in each path $P(\lambda)$, and choose the smallest module in each path which has maximum size jump (among all size jumps greater than a specified threshold); (3) For each module selected at step 2, remove all genes not connected to any other gene in the module; and choose, from all resulting selected modules over λ values, the one with highest standardized score as final selection.

To improve computation speed, an alternative approach was implemented in a more recent version of SigMod we used (available at: <https://github.com/YuanlongLiu/SigMod>). This approach identifies a disease-associated module via finding the smallest λ value (denoted as λ_{opt}) using the binary search algorithm (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binary_search_algorithm). The module selection is determined by two alternative parameters n_{max} and $maxjump$, which are more manipulable than λ and η : n_{max} is the maximum number of genes to be selected in the module (the finally selected module usually has less than n_{max} genes since the genes that do not have any interaction with other selected genes will be removed) and $maxjump$ which is the maximum value of all size jumps in a given selection path.

Assessment of the association of the selected gene module with the disease/trait: We assessed whether the selected final module was significantly associated with the disease/trait (CoA/IgE levels) by estimating the null distribution of the module score using the CGP strategy. The null distribution of the module score is estimated by permuting the SNP-level P-values $n = 100,000$ times and for each CGP sample, the gene-level P-values are recomputed using fastCGP method. Using the recomputed gene P-values, the module score is calculated at each permutation. The observed module score is compared with the module score obtained from the permutation sample to get an empirical p-value.

$$P_{assoc} = \frac{\# \{Z_{m(s)} \geq Z_m\} + 1}{n + 1}$$

3.4 Assessment of the overlap between the two gene modules derived from the CoA-GWAS and IgE-EWAS data

The overlap between the two gene modules selected by the respective network analyses of CoA-GWAS data and IgE-EWAS data was estimated using the similarity coefficient Jaccard Index. The Jaccard index is calculated by $J = n_{shared} / (n_{m_1} + n_{m_2} - n_{shared})$, where n_{shared} denotes the number of genes shared between two modules m_1 and m_2 , n_{m_1} and n_{m_2} denotes the number of genes in the modules m_1 and m_2 respectively. $J = 0$ means there is no overlap between two modules and $J = 1$ signifies the complete overlap of the two modules. Significance of the Jaccard Index was evaluated by the Hypergeometric test.

3.5 Biological interpretation of the identified gene modules

To explore the biological significance of the genes belonging to each of two selected modules, we conducted enrichment analysis (Over Representation Analysis) by analyzing the list of genes in the context of prior biological knowledge. We used the enrichKEGG function of the Bioconductor package clusterProfiler (Yu *et al.*, 2012) to determine whether known biological functions or processes are over-represented in the gene module by fetching the information from the KEGG PATHWAY database on the fly to get the latest pathway information. KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) PATHWAY is a collection of manually drawn pathway maps representing knowledge of the molecular interaction, reaction and relation networks. Currently, there are 541 pathways which cover a wide range of biochemical processes that can be divided in 7 broad categories: metabolism, genetic and environmental information processing, cellular processes, organismal systems, human diseases, and drug development (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2017). The p -values for enrichment were calculated using the hypergeometric test; q -values were estimated for FDR (false-discovery rate) control.

4 Results

We applied the presented strategy to the network analysis of GWAS of Childhood-onset Asthma and EWAS of IgE levels. To build the background network, we used the human PPI network (GeneNet) from the STRING database version 11, which contains information about 19,566 gene products with 11,759,454 relations among them.

4.1 Identification of a gene module enriched with disease/trait association signals

As mentioned earlier, SigMod network analysis needs two inputs – gene P-values and GeneNet – to identify a strongly interconnected module enriched with association signals.

In the first setup, we aimed to identify the gene module associated with Childhood-onset asthma from CoA-GWAS data. As described in Section 2.1, we have summary statistics

for 2,370,689 SNPs from a meta-analysis of nine childhood-onset asthma GWA studies. First, mapping these SNPs to genes according to their position on the genome (human genome build GRCh37) resulted in 985,048 SNP-Gene mappings from 968,400 SNPs having mapped to at least one of 22,094 genes. Using this mapping information, we aggregated SNP-level P-values into gene-level P-values using fastCGP method and converted these gene P-values into gene scores. These gene scores were overlaid onto the GeneNet to construct a scored interaction network. We have only included the interactions with high confidence ($\geq 70\%$) in constructing the network, which resulted in 14,893 nodes and 334,486 edges. SigMod method was then applied to the scored network with parameters λ varying in the interval $[0,1]$ and taking $nmax = 500$ and $maxjump = 10$. We identified a strongly interconnected gene module containing 312 genes with 1,021 connections among them (Figure S1).

In the second setup, we performed the analysis to identify a strongly interconnected module associated with IgE levels from IgE-EWAS data. As described in Section 2.2, we have 2,812,044 CpGs P-values as input from the meta-analysis of EGEA and MRCE EWA studies. To calculate gene-level P-values, we first mapped these CpGs to genes using the GREAT tool, resulting in 832,240 CpG-Gene mappings from 832,195 CpGs having mapped to at least one of 17,057 genes. Similar to the above analysis, we calculated the genes scores for 17,057 genes and constructed a scored GeneNet consisting of 15,333 nodes and 369,880 edges. Applying SigMod with the same parameters as before resulted in a gene module with 253 nodes and 606 edges (Figure S3).

	GWAS data analysis	EWAS data analysis
Genomic regions	2,370,689 SNPs + P-values	2,814,044 CpGs + P-values
Assign SNPs to genes	985,048 SNP-Gene mappings (~ 41% SNPs mapped)	832,240 CpG-Gene mappings (~ 30% CpGs mapped)
Calculate gene statistic	22,094 gene-level scores	17,057 gene-level scores
Construct scored network using established biological network	14,893 nodes & 334,486 edges (~ 36% SNPs, 67% Genes mapped)	15,333 nodes & 369,880 edges (~ 26% CpGs, 89% Genes mapped)
Discover the module associated with the disease	312 nodes & 1,021 edges	253 nodes & 606 edges

Table 4.1: Summary of the steps involved in the analysis strategy, along with the number of SNPs/CpGs/Genes present in each step.

We evaluated the association of each of the gene modules identified by two network analysis with their respective trait (CoA/IgE levels) by applying the CGP strategy. We calculated the module scores for 100,000 CGP evaluations and observed that these scores were not better than the observed modules score as depicted in the Figure 4.1. Thus, we could say that the gene module derived from GWAS is associated with Childhood-onset

Asthma at $P_{assoc} < 10^{-5}$ and the module derived from EWAS is associated with IgE levels at $P_{assoc} < 10^{-5}$.

Figure 4.1: Distribution of the scores of the selected gene modules based on 100,000 random permutations of SNP-level/CpG-level statistics using Circular Genomic Permutation (CGP) strategy. In both cases, none of the permuted module scores was greater than the observed module score.

From Figures S2 and S4, we could observe that > 99% of the genes identified in each of the two modules are nominally associated ($P \leq 0.05$) with the respective trait (CoA/IgE). From Table 4.2, which shows the distribution of the gene best SNP P-values in each selected module, it can be seen that some genes included SNPs associated with childhood-onset asthma or CpGs associated with IgE levels at the genome-wide level ($P \leq 5 \times 10^{-8}$) while most SNPs or CpGs would not have been selected by the CoA GWAS or IgE EWAS.

$P_{best-SNP}$ -value range	GWAS Module	EWAS Module
$\leq 5e-8$	6	1
($5e-8, 5e-7$]	2	0
($5e-7, 5e-6$]	4	7
($5e-6, 5e-5$]	18	23
($5e-5, 5e-4$]	65	119
($5e-4, 5e-3$]	147	97
($5e-3, 5e-2$]	70	6
#genes	312	253

Table 4.2: Distribution of the gene $P_{best-SNP}$ -values of the selected modules, where $P_{best-SNP}$ is the best SNP P-value among all the SNPs mapped to a gene. For example, six genes from GWAS derived module and one gene from EWAS derived module contain $P_{best-SNP} - value < 5 \times 10^{-8}$.

The distribution of gene-level P-values (using fastCGP) is shown in Table 4.3.

P-value range	GWAS Module	EWAS Module
(5e-6, 5e-5]	6	0
(5e-5, 5e-4]	13	1
(5e-4, 5e-3]	67	27
(5e-3, 5e-2]	223	223
> 5e-2	3	2
#genes	312	253

Table 4.3: Distribution of the gene-based P-values for the selected modules. For example, 13 genes from GWAS derived module and one gene from EWAS derived module had P-values within the range $5 \times 10^{-5} < P - \text{value} \leq 5 \times 10^{-4}$.

4.2 Overlap of GWAS and EWAS derived gene modules

We looked at the overlap between the GWAS and EWAS derived gene modules and found 13 genes shared by the CoA-GWAS-derived module (#312 genes) and IgE-EWAS-derived module (#253 genes). The Jaccard index, used to estimate the overlap between these two modules, was $J = 0.02$, with $P_{Hyper} = 7 \times 10^{-4}$. Interestingly, some of these genes (*DRD3*, *TRIM38*) have been reported in recent GWAS related to asthma or immune response phenotypes (Almoguera *et al.*, 2017; Han *et al.*, 2020). We have also identified these genes in the overlap of GWAS and EWAS derived gene modules when we used the Protein Interaction Network Analysis (PINA) network (Cowley *et al.*, 2011) as background instead of STRING's GeneNet.

4.3 Biological Interpretation of the identified gene modules

We performed the KEGG pathway enrichment analysis to understand the biological significance of the genes present in the two modules. With the help of enrichKEGG function from the ClusterProfiler package, we observed that 29 pathways were significantly enriched in genes from the GWAS-derived module ($FDR < 0.05$) (Appendix Table S1). These 29 pathways were mostly related to virus infection, immune related mechanisms, auto immune diseases and Alzheimer's disease (AD) in which immune related mechanisms are known to play a role. It is of note that links between asthma and AD genes were previously found in a network analysis of childhood-onset asthma based on the dmGWAS method (Liu *et al.*, 2017a). Through similar analysis, we observed that two pathways were significantly enriched in genes present in the EWAS-derived module ($FDR < 0.05$), including the AD pathway. Among other pathways at $FDR < 0.2$, we found two pathways related to an auto-immune disease and HIV infection (Appendix Table S2). The overlap between these two sets of pathways indicates the presence of shared biological mechanisms underlying the CoA-GWAS and IgE-levels-EWAS derived modules.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

Biological Network analysis has been successful in gaining insights on the joint effects of multiple genomic factors which could not be obtained from single-SNP analysis. These new insights would aid in having a better understanding of the mechanisms underlying the disease. We have employed a biological network analysis approach to understand the shared mechanisms underlying childhood-onset asthma and IgE levels using GWAS and EWAS data respectively. The proposed approach included mapping genome-wide association results to genes, calculating gene-level statistic, generating a scored network with the help of publicly available protein-protein interaction network, identifying a strongly interconnected gene module enriched with association signals, followed by the module overlap analysis and biological interpretation of the identified modules. This approach allowed us to identify a module associated with childhood-onset asthma, containing 312 genes with 1,021 connections among them, and another gene module associated with IgE levels, including 253 nodes and 606 interactions. The GWAS-derived module contains 28 genes having at least 20 connections within the selected module with $P_{best-SNP} values = \{5.74 \times 10^{-5}, 1.66 \times 10^{-2}\}$. Meanwhile, the EWAS-derived module contains 3 genes with at least 20 connections within the module with $P_{best-CpG} values = \{2.61 \times 10^{-4}, 6.09 \times 10^{-4}\}$. This outlines that SigMod not only rewards high-degree genes but also significant genes. These SNPs and CpGs would have been missed by single-SNP analysis or single-CpG analysis, which illustrates the advantage of incorporating network analysis for reducing the search space in pinpointing the disease-associated genes. The GWAS and EWAS-derived modules share 13 genes and enrichment analysis of these modules also points to shared biological pathways, which shows that our strategy enables characterizing biological mechanisms underlying both risk of childhood-onset asthma and regulation of IgE production.

In this work, we mapped SNPs to genes according to their position on the genome by using a stringent definition of gene boundaries, which were represented by the start site and 3' untranslated region of each gene to reduce false positives. Our mapping strategy resulted in mapping around 41% of the SNPs to genes. This mapping percentage could be increased by extending boundaries to flanking regions of a gene. However, this extension needs to be carefully assessed as it may result in increasing the degree of overlap among nearby genes, which in turn may increase false SNP-to-gene mappings. Another annotation strategy to consider is functional-based mapping using gene expression through expression quantitative trait loci (eQTLs) or by defining the regulatory domain for each gene as performed in the CpG to gene mapping (McLean *et al.*, 2010; Pickrell, 2014). Furthermore, mapping strategies including the non-coding regulatory regions should be examined, as only a small fraction of GWAS SNPs are protein-coding variants (Albert and Kruglyak, 2015).

The performance of network analysis is heavily dependent on the quality of the background biological network used. So, we have used the STRING protein-protein

interaction as background with only high-confidence interactions. Due to this choice, a high proportion of interactions on the STRING network have been removed from downstream analysis. As the analysis includes only high confident interactions, the interactions present in the identified module are highly reliable. Decreasing the confidence of the interactions (for example, to medium-confidence interactions) might increase the network size and thereby might shed light on newer pathways which were not found in the analysis with high-confidence interactions.

In summary, we presented a strategy for the identification of a gene module associated with the phenotype of interest using network science principles and detection of genes shared by modules derived from two types of omics data (GWAS and EWAS summary statistics). This strategy identified two gene modules associated with CoA (using GWAS outcomes) and IgE-levels (using EWAS outcomes). We detected an overlap between these modules which share relevant genes and biological pathways. With the success of the presented strategy applied to medium-size datasets, we aim to extend this strategy to larger datasets to gain further insights into the mechanism underlying childhood-onset asthma and IgE levels. Though this strategy has been tested on the analysis of genomics and epigenomics results, the principles can be applied to any type of omics data.

Funding and Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 813533. This project was also supported by the European Commission Research Grant for the Gabriel Consortium (LSHB-CT-2006-018996) and PHRC-CL-20131610 EVADA and ANR-15-EPIG-004-05-RESET-AID grants. We also thank the EGEA cooperative group (<https://egeanet.vjf.inserm.fr/index.php/en/egea-group-en>)

References

- Albert, F.W. and Kruglyak, L. (2015) The role of regulatory variation in complex traits and disease. *Nat Rev Genet*, **16**, 197–212.
- Allum, F. *et al.* (2019) Dissecting features of epigenetic variants underlying cardiometabolic risk using full-resolution epigenome profiling in regulatory elements. *Nat Commun*, **10**, 1209.
- Almoguera, B. *et al.* (2017) Identification of Four Novel Loci in Asthma in European American and African American Populations. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*, **195**, 456–463.
- Andiappan, A.K. *et al.* (2016) Functional variants of 17q12-21 are associated with allergic asthma but not allergic rhinitis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*, **137**, 758-766.e3.
- Azencott, C.-A. *et al.* (2013) Efficient network-guided multi-locus association mapping with graph cuts. *Bioinformatics*, **29**, i171–i179.
- Beaumier, L. *et al.* (2019) Epigenome-wide association study of Immunoglobulin E levels using high-resolution DNA methylation profiling. 28th annual meeting of the International Genetic Epidemiology Society (IGES), Houston, Texas, USA, 12-14 October 2019. *Genet Epidemiol*, 874. doi: 10.1002/gepi.22256
- Burrows, B. *et al.* (1989) Association of Asthma with Serum IgE Levels and Skin-Test Reactivity to Allergens. *N Engl J Med*, **320**, 271–277.
- Cabrera, C.P. *et al.* (2012) Uncovering networks from genome-wide association studies via circular genomic permutation. *G3 (Bethesda)*, **2**, 1067–1075.
- Cowley, M.J. *et al.* (2011) PINA v2. 0: mining interactome modules. *Nucleic Acids Res*, **40**, D862–D865.
- Demenais, F. *et al.* (2018) Multiancestry association study identifies new asthma risk loci that colocalize with immune-cell enhancer marks. *Nat Genet*, **50**, 42–53.
- Eddy, S. *et al.* (2020) Integrated multi-omics approaches to improve classification of chronic kidney disease. *Nat Rev Nephrol*, **16**, 657–668.
- Ferreira, M.A.R. *et al.* (2019) Genetic Architectures of Childhood- and Adult-Onset Asthma Are Partly Distinct. *Am J Hum Genet*, **104**, 665–684.
- Han, Y. *et al.* (2020) Genome-wide analysis highlights contribution of immune system pathways to the genetic architecture of asthma. *Nat Commun*, **11**, 1776.
- Jia, P. *et al.* (2011) dmGWAS: dense module searching for genome-wide association studies in protein–protein interaction networks. *Bioinformatics*, **27**, 95–102.
- Kanehisa, M. *et al.* (2017) KEGG: new perspectives on genomes, pathways, diseases and drugs. *Nucleic Acids Res*, **45**, D353–D361.
- Karczewski, K.J. and Snyder, M.P. (2018) Integrative omics for health and disease. *Nat Rev Genet*, **19**, 299–310.
- Liang, L. *et al.* (2015) An epigenome-wide association study of total serum immunoglobulin E concentration. *Nature*, **520**, 670–674.
- Liu, Y. *et al.* (2017a) Network-assisted analysis of GWAS data identifies a functionally-relevant gene module for childhood-onset asthma. *Sci Rep*, **7**, 938.
- Liu, Y. *et al.* (2017b) SigMod: an exact and efficient method to identify a strongly interconnected disease-associated module in a gene network. *Bioinformatics*, **10**, 1536-1544.
- Ma, X. *et al.* (2020) Integrative genomics analysis of various omics data and networks identify risk genes and variants vulnerable to childhood-onset asthma. *BMC Med Genomics*, **13**, 123.

- McLean,C.Y. *et al.* (2010) GREAT improves functional interpretation of cis-regulatory regions. *Nat Biotechnol*, **28**, 495–501.
- Moffatt,M.F. *et al.* (2010) A large-scale, consortium-based genomewide association study of asthma. *N Engl J Med*, **363**, 1211–1221.
- Oliver,S. (2000) Proteomics: Guilt-by-association goes global. *Nature*, **403**, 601–603.
- Pickrell,J.K. (2014) Joint Analysis of Functional Genomic Data and Genome-wide Association Studies of 18 Human Traits. *Am J Hum Genet*, **94**, 559–573.
- Piovesan,D. *et al.* (2015) Protein function prediction using guilty by association from interaction networks. *Amino Acids*, **47**, 2583–2592.
- Szklarczyk,D. *et al.* (2019) STRING v11: protein-protein association networks with increased coverage, supporting functional discovery in genome-wide experimental datasets. *Nucleic Acids Res*, **47**, D607–D613.
- Wang,Q. *et al.* (2015) EW_dmGWAS: edge-weighted dense module search for genome-wide association studies and gene expression profiles. *Bioinformatics*, **15**, 2591-4.
- Wolfe,C.J. *et al.* (2005) Systematic survey reveals general applicability of "guilt-by-association" within gene coexpression networks. *BMC Bioinformatics*, **6**, 227.
- Yu,G. *et al.* (2012) clusterProfiler: an R Package for Comparing Biological Themes Among Gene Clusters. *OMICS*, **16**, 284–287.
- Gu,Z. (2020) rGREAT: Client for GREAT Analysis. <https://github.com/jokergoo/rGREAT>, <http://great.stanford.edu/public/html/>. Bioconductor.

Appendix

- A1: Gene module associated with Childhood-Onset Asthma

Figure S1: Pattern of interactions among the module genes identified by the network analysis of Childhood-Onset asthma GWAS data.

- A2: Distribution of P-values present in the CoA-GWAS-derived gene module

Figure S2: Histogram of the gene P-values ($n=312$) of the selected gene module from Childhood-Onset asthma GWAS data (in blue) and the gene P-values of all the genes (14,893) present in the background network (in grey). $> 99\%$ of the 312 genes are nominally associated ($P \leq 0.05$) with CoA. The bottom figure is a zoomed view of the top figure.

- A3: Gene module associated with IgE-levels

Figure S3: Pattern of interactions among the module genes identified by the network analysis of IgE EWAS data.

- A4: Distribution of P-values present in the IgE-EWAS-derived gene module

Figure S4: Histogram of the gene P-values ($n=253$) of the selected gene module from IgE EWAS data (in blue) and the gene P-values of all the genes (15,333) present in the background network (in grey). $> 99\%$ of the 253 genes are nominally associated ($P \leq 0.05$) with IgE-levels. The bottom figure is a zoomed view of the top figure.

- A5: KEGG pathways enriched in genes from the Childhood-Onset Asthma-GWAS selected module

KEGG ID	Pathway Description	q-value	#Genes
hsa05166	Human T-cell leukemia virus 1 infection	6.74E-08	23
hsa05169	Epstein-Barr virus infection	7.90E-06	19
hsa05167	Kaposi sarcoma-associated herpesvirus infection	1.39E-03	15
hsa04612	Antigen processing and presentation	2.45E-03	9
hsa04922	Glucagon signaling pathway	4.13E-03	10
hsa04145	Phagosome	4.13E-03	12
hsa05203	Viral carcinogenesis	4.36E-03	14
hsa05034	Alcoholism	5.53E-03	13
hsa04120	Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis	5.53E-03	11
hsa04919	Thyroid hormone signaling pathway	5.96E-03	10
hsa04940	Type I diabetes mellitus	5.96E-03	6
hsa04218	Cellular senescence	1.05E-02	11
hsa05230	Central carbon metabolism in cancer	1.29E-02	7
hsa04658	Th1 and Th2 cell differentiation	1.31E-02	8
hsa05330	Allograft rejection	1.84E-02	5
hsa04640	Hematopoietic cell lineage	1.85E-02	8
hsa05416	Viral myocarditis	2.33E-02	6
hsa05332	Graft-versus-host disease	2.43E-02	5
hsa05170	Human immunodeficiency virus 1 infection	2.57E-02	12
hsa04066	HIF-1 signaling pathway	2.72E-02	8
hsa05161	Hepatitis B	2.76E-02	10
hsa05322	Systemic lupus erythematosus	2.76E-02	9
hsa03050	Proteasome	2.85E-02	5
hsa05163	Human cytomegalovirus infection	3.32E-02	12
hsa05017	Spinocerebellar ataxia	3.40E-02	9
hsa05310	Asthma	3.52E-02	4
hsa05320	Autoimmune thyroid disease	4.50E-02	5
hsa05020	Prion disease	4.94E-02	13
hsa05010	Alzheimer disease	4.94E-02	16

Table S1: 29 KEGG pathways enriched in genes belonging to the selected module from network analysis of Childhood-Onset Asthma GWAS data along with the q-values and number of module genes in each pathway. For simplicity, pathways with $q_value \leq 0.05$ have been included in this table.

- A6: KEGG pathways enriched in genes from the IgE-EWAS selected module

KEGG ID	Pathway Description	q-value	#Genes
hsa04371	Apelin signaling pathway	2.91E-02	11
hsa05010	Alzheimer disease	2.91E-02	19

hsa05012	Parkinson disease	1.25E-01	13
hsa04966	Collecting duct acid secretion	1.25E-01	4
hsa05014	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	1.59E-01	16
hsa05320	Autoimmune thyroid disease	1.59E-01	5
hsa05170	Human immunodeficiency virus 1 infection	1.59E-01	11
hsa03010	Ribosome	1.66E-01	9
hsa04370	VEGF signaling pathway	1.91E-01	5

Table S2: Nine KEGG pathways enriched in genes belonging to the selected module from the network analysis of IgE EWAS data along with the q-values and number of module genes in each pathway. For simplicity, pathways with $q_value \leq 0.2$ have been included in this table.